

PRISMA Checklist – Systematic Review: Bender- Gestalt Visual-Motor Test in Young Subjects

PRISMA Item	Presence and description	Location in the manuscript
Title	The title indicates that the report is a systematic review	Title page
Abstract	Structured abstract provided with background, methods, results, and conclusion	Abstract
Introduction – Rationale	Rationale and clinical interest of the review are clearly explained	Introduction
Introduction – Objectives	The objective of the review is clearly stated	Introduction
Methods – Eligibility criteria	Clear inclusion and exclusion criteria described	Methods – Eligibility criteria
Methods – Information sources	Databases and years searched are provided	Methods – Search strategy
Methods – Search strategy	Detailed search terms and strategies for each database	Methods – Search strategy
Methods – Selection process	Screening and selection process including number of reviewers	Methods – Study selection + Figure 1
Methods – Data collection process	Process of data extraction described	Methods – Data extraction
Methods – Data items	Main data items extracted from studies are listed	Methods – Data extraction
Methods – Study risk of bias assessment	Risk of bias assessment tool and procedure described	Methods – Quality assessment
Methods – Effect measures	Narrative synthesis described, no statistical pooling	Methods – Data synthesis
Methods – Risk of bias in studies	Method for evaluating risk of bias in included studies	Methods – Quality assessment
Methods – Certainty of evidence	Certainty of evidence briefly addressed in discussion	Discussion – Limitations
Results – Study selection	Number of studies at each stage and reasons for exclusion provided	Results – Study selection + Figure 1
Results – Study characteristics	Characteristics of each included study summarized	Results – Study characteristics + Table 1
Results – Risk of bias in studies	Risk of bias results presented	Results – Risk of bias + Table 2

Results – Results of individual studies	Key outcomes from each included study presented	Results – Table 3
Results – Results of syntheses	Findings synthesized narratively	Results – Summary of findings
Results – Sensitivity analyses	Not applicable; no sensitivity analysis was performed	N/A
Discussion – Summary of evidence	Main results summarized in context	Discussion
Discussion – Limitations of evidence	Limitations of the included studies described	Discussion – Limitations
Discussion – Limitations of the review	Limitations of the review process acknowledged	Discussion – Limitations
Discussion – Interpretation	Findings interpreted considering objectives, evidence, and limitations	Discussion + Conclusion
Other – Funding	Funding source declared	Acknowledgments
Other – Competing interests	Competing interests disclosed	Conflict of interest section
Other – Data availability	Data availability statement included	Data availability section

FIGURE 1: Flow chart of study selection process and results